

A Novel Transformer Model with Multiple Instances Learning for Diabetic Retinopathy Classification

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Abstract- Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is a leading cause of vision impairment among diabetic patients, and its timely detection is crucial for preventing irreversible vision loss. This work presents a novel hybrid model that combines Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), EfficientNetB0, Transformer architectures, and Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) for accurate DR classification and recommendation. EfficientNetB0 serves as a lightweight yet powerful backbone for extracting high-quality features from retinal fundus images, while the Transformer module captures global context and spatial relationships across image regions. MIL enhances model robustness by treating each image as a collection of instances, allowing effective learning even with limited or weak labels. Additionally, the system provides severity-based recommendations to assist clinicians in prioritizing patient care. Experimental results across multiple DR datasets demonstrate superior accuracy, generalization, and clinical relevance, highlighting the model's potential for integration into real-world diabetic screening workflows.

Keywords: Diabetic Retinopathy(DR), Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)EfficientNetB0, Transformer, Multiple Instance Learning (MIL).

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is a progressive eye disease caused by damage to the retinal blood vessels due to prolonged hyperglycemia in diabetic patients. It remains one of the leading causes of preventable blindness globally, particularly in working-age adults. Early detection and accurate classification of DR are critical for effective intervention and timely treatment. However, manual screening of retinal images is time-consuming, prone to inter-observer variability, and not scalable for large populations. Consequently, the development of automated and reliable computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems has become a pressing research priority in medical imaging and artificial intelligence.

Recent advances in deep learning, particularly Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), have significantly improved the performance of automated DR detection systems. CNNs are highly effective in extracting local features and spatial patterns from fundus images. Among various CNN architectures, EfficientNetB0 has gained attention for

its ability to achieve high accuracy with fewer parameters and reduced computational cost, making it well-suited for real-world deployment. However, traditional CNNs often struggle to capture long-range dependencies and contextual relationships across different regions of the retina, which are vital for understanding disease severity and progression.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Title: Automated Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy using Deep Learning

Author: Carson Lam, MD, 1 Darwin Yi

Year: 2020

Description: Diabetic retinopathy is a leading cause of blindness among working-age adults. Early detection of this condition is critical for good prognosis. In this paper, we demonstrate the use of on color fundus images for the recognition task of diabetic retinopathy staging. Our network models achieved test metric performance comparable to baseline literature results, with validation sensitivity of 95%. We additionally explored multinomial classification models, and demonstrate that errors

primarily occur in the misclassification of mild disease as normal due to the CNNs inability to detect subtle disease features. We discovered that preprocessing with contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization and ensuring dataset fidelity by expert verification of class labels improves recognition of subtle features. Transfer learning on pretrained GoogLeNet and AlexNet models from ImageNet improved peak test set accuracies to 74.5%, 68.8%, and 57.2% on 2-ary, 3-ary, and 4-ary classification models, respectively.

Title: Diabetic Retinopathy Early Detection Based on OCT and OCTA Feature Fusion

Author: Nabila Eladawi, Ahmed ElTanboly

Year: 2019

Description: Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is one of the major causes of blindness worldwide. It is a diabetes complication that occurs after the damage of the blood vessels in the light-sensitive tissue in the retina. So, early detection of DR could reduce the severity of the disease and help ophthalmologists in treating and investigating it more efficiently. In this paper, we developed a computeraided diagnosis (CAD) system that can detect early signs of DR using both optical coherence tomography (OCT) and optical coherence tomography angiography (OCTA) images. Our system is able to segment the blood vessels from two retinal plexuses using OCTA images. Also, it segments twelve different retinal layers from OCT scans. Then, seven different features are extracted from both segmented OCTA plexuses and OCT layers. Finally, these features are fused to generate a comprehensive diagnostic non-invasive tool for detecting early signs of DR. A total number of 76 cases (23 normal and 53 DR) were used in evaluating the performance of the proposed systems. Using 4-fold cross-validation, our proposed system achieved an average accuracy of 100%. These results show the potential of the proposed system.

Title: Diabetic Retinopathy: Present and Past

Author: AnkitaGuptaa, RitaChhikarab

Year: 2019

Description: Diabetes, a chronic disease affects various organs of human body including the retina. Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) results from the Diabetes Mellitus (DM). In literature various machine learning

algorithms have been applied in detection of DR. This involves two steps; Feature extraction and Classification. This paper reviews the various techniques used for detecting DR based on the features like blood vessels, microaneurysms, haemorrhages etc. In most of the experiments retinal fundus images were used in which images of retina were captured by fundus camera. This review bifurcates the detection of DR into two approaches; Blood vessels segmentation and Identification of lesions. This paper compares the experimental results of various machine learning techniques based on parameters like sensitivity, specificity, Area Under Curve (AUC), Accuracy. The results are also compared with the deep neural networks and analysis of best technique has been provided.

Title: Feedback on a Publicly Distributed Image

Database: The Messidor Database

Author: Guy Cazuguel

Year: 2020

Description: The Messidor database, which contains hundreds of eye fundus images, has been publicly distributed since 2008. It was created by the Messidor project in order to evaluate automatic lesion segmentation and diabetic retinopathy grading methods. Designing, producing and maintaining such a database entails significant costs. By publicly sharing it, one hopes to bring a valuable resource to the public research community. However, the real interest and benefit of the research community is not easy to quantify. We analyse here the feedback on the Messidor database, after more than 6 years of diffusion. This analysis should apply to other similar research databases.

Title: Detection and classification of diabetic retinopathy using K-means clustering and fuzzy logic

Author: Md. Jahiruzzaman, A.B.M. Aowlad Hossain

Year: 2019

Description: Diabetic retinopathy is a common vision threatening disease which occurs due to the abnormalities in retina of diabetic patients. Detection of diabetic retinopathy is crucial for prevention of loss of vision and diagnosis of diabetic. As fundus are sensitive to vascular syndromes, efficient detection of diabetic retinopathy related

exudates and hemorrhages in fundus images of the retina can be a helpful for effective screening. This study presents an effective approach to detect exudates and hemorrhages in retinal fundus image and classify the diabetic retinopathy with reasonable cost. A k-means color compression technique is used to cluster the fundus image in different region of interest reducing color dimension. The different parts of diabetic fundus then segmented out and analyzed through the region properties attributes. Finally, the recognition of diabetic retinopathy was done by the knowledge based fuzzy inference system (FIS) with these effective attributes through experiment and trail basis. The sensitivity and accuracy of the detector is found as 98.2% and 92.3% respectively. The HRF retinal fundus image database images are successfully classified by fuzzy logic classifier with accuracy up to 96.67%.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system integrates CNN, EfficientNetB0, Transformer, and Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) to enhance Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) classification. EfficientNetB0 extracts efficient and high-quality features from retinal fundus images. The Transformer captures global dependencies across image patches, improving contextual understanding. MIL treats each image as a bag of instances, enabling robust learning from weakly labeled data. Additionally, the system provides severity-based recommendations to assist clinicians in treatment planning.

IV. MODULES

Data Acquisition and Preprocessing Module:

This module focuses on obtaining high-quality retinal fundus images from reliable medical image sources. To ensure the data is suitable for model training, several preprocessing techniques are applied. These include resizing the images to a uniform dimension, enhancing contrast to highlight key retinal features, applying noise reduction to improve clarity, and normalizing pixel values to maintain consistency. These steps help standardize the input data and improve the effectiveness of the

feature extraction and classification processes in the later stages of the model.

Feature Extraction Module (CNN + EfficientNetB0):

as the primary backbone for feature extraction due to its efficient scaling and reduced computational complexity. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are used to detect critical features such as microaneurysms, hemorrhages, and exudates. The output feature maps from this stage represent meaningful spatial patterns necessary for classifying different stages of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Transformer-Based Global Context Module:

To capture long-range dependencies and contextual relationships among different regions of the fundus images, the model incorporates a Transformer architecture. By dividing the feature map into patches, the Transformer applies self-attention mechanisms to learn spatial correlations across the image. This global context awareness enhances the model's ability to detect subtle or dispersed signs of DR that may be overlooked by local feature-based methods.

Multiple Instance Learning (MIL) Module:

This module treats each input image as a bag of multiple instances (patches or feature regions), enabling the model to handle weak or partial labels. MIL helps the system learn from cases where only image-level labels are available, without needing precise annotations for each lesion. This significantly improves model robustness and classification accuracy, particularly in real-world scenarios with incomplete ground truth.

V. RECOMMENDATION AND DIAGNOSIS MODULE:

Based on the predicted severity level of DR, this module provides intelligent recommendations to assist ophthalmologists. These may include follow-up timelines, referral suggestions, or potential treatment paths. The system is designed for integration into clinical platforms, offering a user-friendly interface that supports automated diagnosis, reduces screening workload, and

promotes early intervention for high-risk patients. learns the features of the image, and classifies them based on the learned features.

V. CONCLUSION

Diabetic Retinopathy is a serious complication of diabetes that requires early detection to prevent vision loss. This project leverages Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to develop an automated system for detecting DR from retinal fundus images. By utilizing deep learning techniques, the proposed model improves diagnostic accuracy, reduces manual screening efforts, and enhances accessibility to quality eye care. The system's ability to classify different stages of DR efficiently makes it a valuable tool for ophthalmologists and healthcare professionals. Future enhancements may focus on improving model interpretability, expanding dataset diversity, and integrating real-time screening for widespread clinical adoption.

VI. RESULT

Figure 1: Command prompt

Figure2: Initializing the Server

Fig 3: Login page

Fig 4: output page

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